

Analysis of vitamin C content in samples of different origin

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Direct current and differential pulse polarographic methods have been developed for the analysis of ascorbic acid (vitamin C) in samples of different origin. Vitamin C produced a well defined polarographic wave/peak in BR buffer at pH 6.5 ± 0.1 with $E_{1/2}/E_p = -0.065/-0.060$ V vs SCE. The results are in excellent agreement to the reported values. The statistical analysis of the observed data reveals high accuracy and precision.

There are a number of techniques like ^{13}C NMR¹, chromometric determination² modified electrodes³, spectroscopy⁴ etc. for the determination of vitamin C in samples. Interestingly, vitamin C produces good polarographic responses and can be determined qualitatively and quantitatively using polarographic methods of analysis⁵. Looking at the oligo determination capability, extraordinary determination sensitivity, rapidity, low cost and accuracy of these methods, the authors have selected differential pulse polarography (DPP) and direct current polarography

(DCP) for the analysis of ascorbic acid in the samples of different origin, the results of which are reported here.

Results and Discussion

In Britton-Robinson buffer ascorbic acid gives a well defined reversible reduction wave with $E_{1/2} = -0.065$ V and $E_p = -0.060$ V vs SCE at pH 6.5 ± 0.1 . The height of the wave/peak was found to be proportional to the vitamin concentration. The number of electrons involved in the electrode process was two as calculated by the measure-

Table 1 Results on samples of various origin for their vitamin C content (mg %)*

Sample	Parameter ^a	DCP		DPP		Reported in literature
		Added	Found	Added	Found	
(a) Multi-vitamin capsule ^b	Amount	-	62.56	-	62.54	-
		52.80	115.20	52.80	115.28	-
	% R		99.8		99.9	-
	RMD		0.001		0.0007	-1
	SD		0.03		0.01	-
	CV		0.01		0.006	-
	Final analysis results			62.56		62.54
(b) Lemon juice	Amount	-	45.0	-	45.10	-
		52.80	97.40	52.80	99.60	-
	% R		99.5		99.6	-
	RMD		0.005		0.002	-
	SD		0.32		0.16	-
	CV		0.07		0.35	-
	Final analysis results			45.00		45.10
(c) Milk	Amount	-	4.00	-	4.05	-
		3.52	7.50	3.52	7.56	-
	% R		99.7		99.8	-
	RMD		0.010		0.009	-
	SD		0.08		0.05	-
	CV		0.02		0.11	-
	Final analysis results			4.00		4.05

*Average of four determinations ^a%R = Percentage recovery, RMD = relative mean deviation, SD = standard deviation, CV = coefficient of variance

^bReported by the manufacturer.

ment of $E_{3/4}-E_{1/4}$ values. Log plot slope of the reduction wave shows the reaction to be reversible.

The enediol group of ascorbic acid is electroactive and is capable of undergoing a two-electron change at the electrode⁶.

The presence of other compounds like pyridoxin does not effect the determination. The concentration of ascorbic acid in unknown samples was calculated with the help of calibration curve and by standard addition method. The statistical analysis of the results is shown in Table 1. Percentage recovery was more than 99.5% in each case. The values of relative mean deviation, standard deviation and coefficient of variance which were < 0.01 , < 0.32 and < 0.35 , respectively, speak the reliability of the data. The final analysis results of ascorbic acid in samples of various origin (Table 1) are in good agreement with those reported in the literature.

Looking at the oligo determination capability, extra ordinary detection sensitively, rapidity, simplicity, low cost and accuracy, the polarographic methods can be recommended for such analysis.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Double-distilled water was used to prepare the solutions. A 0.01 M solution of ascorbic acid was prepared in distilled water. BR buffer (mixture of 0.04 M phosphoric acid, 0.04 M acetic acid and 0.04 M boric acid) was prepared⁷.

The DCP and DPP studies were carried out on an Elico CL-357 DC polarograph and Elico CL-90 pulse polarograph, respectively. A Systronic 35 pH meter was used. Polarographic cell consisted of a three-electrode assembly with a calomal electrode (reference electrode) and platinum electrode (auxiliary electrode), the working electrode being a dropping mercury electrode (DME). The capillary characteristic of the DME had $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ values of $2.5 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60 cm effective height of mercury column.

Determination of vitamin C : A known concentration of vitamin C was taken in a polarographic cell having 10 ml of BR buffer. The volume of the test solution was made up to 100 ml with distilled water and a 0.2 N NaOH solution was added to adjust the pH to 6.5 ± 0.1 . The test solution was deaerated by passing purified hydrogen gas for 10 min before recording the polarogram, keeping the initial emf set to -0.0 V .

Calibration curve was obtained by taking varying concentrations of ascorbic acid, and the polarograms were recorded under the above experimental conditions.

The sample of pharmaceutical formulation was converted to analyte and polarograms were recorded with minimum delay so that no significant change in ascorbic acid took place prior to analysis⁸. Lemon juice and buffalo milk samples were also analysed by the proposed methods. Polarograms were recorded under the same experimental conditions as discussed earlier.

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